

OPTIMAL WEIGHT OF COMMERCIAL SECTOR AND REPRODUCTION SCHEME**

Keywords: *commercial sector, reproduction scheme, transformation problem, equalized profit rate*

Расширенная аннотация на русском языке¹

Когда схема воспроизводства Маркса появилась во втором томе «Капитала», в ней не было специального коммерческого сектора, даже когда речь шла о процессе обращения, и, следовательно, той схемы недостаточно для анализа реального процесса обращения. Однако Маркс планировал добавить коммерческий сектор в свою «Таблицу» (которая позже была осуществлена именно как схема воспроизводства) в соответствии с его рукописями 1861–63 гг. Более того, Маркс говорил, что в первом проекте тома 2 «Капитала» заявлялось, что он планирует дать некоторые положения о роли коммерческого капитала в процессе воспроизводства в конце третьего тома. Другими словами, это была незаконченная задача, которую признал сам Маркс, и марксистские экономисты продолжили пытаться

включить коммерческий сектор в схему воспроизводства.

Тем не менее, все новые японские исследования в этой области имеют различного рода проблемы. Например, чрезвычайно сложная и непонятная формулировка, не уравнивающая нормы прибыли между промышленным сектором и коммерческим сектором. Эти недостатки возникают из-за методологической слабости, заключающейся в том, что они не могут использовать какие-либо математические уравнения, а используют только числовые примеры, а затраты, такие как s , v , не могут быть пересчитаны, чтобы соответствовать ценовым изменениям в ходе рыночных превращений.

Поэтому данная работа включает рыночный сектор в схему воспроизводства Маркса, не используя числовые примеры, а формулируя систему математических уравнений. Это совершенно неадекватно непосредственному обращению к рыночному сектору, что происходит только после перераспределения прибавочной стоимости, произведен-

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ной в промышленном капитале (производственном секторе). Это связано с тем, что коммерческий сектор может существовать, если ему гарантируется та же норма прибыли, что и в промышленном секторе (производственном секторе), но при этом он не производит стоимость сам по себе. В этом смысле невозможно обсуждать рыночный сектор на макроэкономическом уровне, пренебрегая выравниванием ставок прибыли.

В этом смысле данная работа впервые вводит трёхсекторную схему воспроизводства следующим образом:

$$W_1 = c_1 + v_1 + m_1$$

$$W_2 = c_2 + v_2 + m_2$$

$$W_c = c_c + v_c + m_c,$$

а затем, уточняет роль коммерческого (рыночного) сектора, сокращающего период обращения. В этом состоит причина, по которой производственные сектора переносят свою прибавочную стоимость в коммерческий сектор. Предположим, что Δp — первоначальная продолжительность времени производства, Δc — первоначальная продолжительность времени обращения, $\Delta c'$ — сокращенная продолжительность времени обращения из-за деятельности коммерческого капитала с прибавочной стоимостью m , первоначально произведенной промышленным капиталом. В этом случае промышленный капитал может увеличить время производства в

$$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p}$$

несколько раз и произвести дополнительную сумму прибавочной стоимости

$$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} m$$

, которая покрывает издержки и прибыль коммерческого сектора.

Базируясь на этом понимании и проведя процедуру некоторых преоб-

разований, данная работа приходит в итоге к следующей системе уравнений:

$$W_1^* = \left(c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c} \right)$$

$$W_2^* = \left(c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c} \right)$$

$$W_c^* = z \left(c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \right) \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c}$$

Этот результат показывает несколько важных моментов. Они заключаются в следующем:

1. Как видно на первом этапе преобразований, первые два уравнения, в предположении, что $W_1^* + W_2^* = W_1 + W_2$, могут определять три переменные: W_1^* , W_2^* и r^* , независимые от коммерческого сектора. Другими словами, рынок вообще не обязуется определять одинаковую норму прибыли, а просто принимает её как таковую.

2. Общий объём продаж на рынке W_c^* может быть переписан как

$$z \frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*} (W_1^* + W_2^*) = z \frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*} (W_1 + W_2)$$

а это означает, что он в $\frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*}$ раз больше, чем общее производство в промышленных секторах.

3. Конечно, прибыль коммерческого сектора также должна быть в $\frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*}$ раз больше, чем общая прибыль промышленных секторов, и $\frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*}$ определяется частично существующими технологиями Δp , Δc и $\Delta c'$ и частично r^* , который определяется промышленными секторами.

В заключение мы могли бы показать, что 1) прибавочная стоимость в коммерческом секторе не производится в этом секторе, а просто перераспределяется из промышленного сектора, но 2) коммерческий сектор (рынок) может поднять производство прибавочной стоимости путем сокращения периода обращения для производственного сектора и 3) рынок может занимать определенный вес во всей экономике, имея в виду его влияние на период произ-

водства (Δp), период обращения (Δc) и сокращение отношения к периоду обращения ($\Delta c - \Delta c'$) и, наконец, 4) средняя норма прибыли определяется только промышленными секторами без учета коммерческих секторов (рынка).

Introduction

Since Marx's reproduction scheme was introduced in Volume 2 of *Capital*, there was no unique commercial sector in his reproduction scheme, even if it discussed circulation process, and hence this scheme is not enough to analyze the real circulation process. However, Yano (1991) and Murakami (2014) argue, Marx planned to add the commercial sector in his 'Tableau' (which later came to fruition as the reproduction scheme) according to his manuscripts of 1861-63. Furthermore, Marx stated, in the first draft of Volume 2 of *Capital*, that he was planning to give his some provisions in the reproduction process of commercial capital at the end of the third volume. In other words, it was an unfinished task that Marx himself acknowledged, and Marxian economists have continued to try to incorporate the commercial sector into the reproduction scheme. In Japan, the most prominent achievement in this field are Yano (2006) and Murakami (2014, 2017).

However, commercial capital is shown outside of the reproduction scheme in Yano (2006), and his formalization is extremely complicated and incomprehensible. Furthermore, Murakami (2014, 2017) also remain a problem that the profit rate is not equalized between the industrial sector and the commercial sector. This shortage comes from his methodological weakness that he could not use any mathematical equations but only numerical examples, and costs such as c, v could be not recalculated to correspond to the price

change by the transformation in table-5 and 6 in Murakami (2014).

Therefore, this paper incorporates the commercial sector into Marx's reproduction scheme not using numerical examples but formulating a mathematical equation system. This is decisively inadequate to treat the commercial sector, which only takes place after redistribution of the surplus value produced in industrial capital (productive sector). This is because the commercial sector can exist by being guaranteed the same profit rate as the industrial sector (productive sector) without producing value by itself. In this sense, it is not possible to discuss the commercial sector on the macroeconomic level neglecting the equalization of the profit rates.

In this sense, this paper introduces mathematical variable system instead of numerical examples, and shows a new reproduction scheme which also includes the commercial sector with its equalized profit rate to the industrial sector.

Three Sector Reproduction Scheme with Equalized Profit Rate Including Commercial Sector

Therefore, our first task is to introduce a new value-term reproduction scheme which includes the commercial sector, and it is already tried by above-mentioned Yano (2006) and Murakami (2014) with other sectors, for example, with a sector to produce the materials of money and the materials of means of production. However, in order to simplify this system, we neglect these two sectors and add the commercial sector only into the original reproduction scheme. That is,

$$\begin{aligned} W_1 &= c_1 + v_1 + m_1 \\ W_2 &= c_2 + v_2 + m_2 \\ W_c &= c_c + v_c + m_c^2 \end{aligned}$$

² This is Obata (2009)'s way to express reproduction scheme.

Here, suffixes c indicates the commercial sector which does not produce any value, and this cc must cover the total amount of W_1+W_2 divided by the number of turn-overs, since the commercial sector must transact all the goods of this society. Here we assume that. Furthermore, what should be explained at first here is that the reproduction scheme in volume 2 of *Capital* is formulated as the two industrial sectors engage its circulation to sell their products by themselves without help by the commercial sector. This can be theoretically assumed. However, this paper does not introduce this assumption, and express explicitly the commercial sector as the third equation which does not produce any value. Therefore, at the level of value, W_c should be zero, while W_1 and W_2 are positive. This fact can be confirmed by examining the intersectoral transactions among three sectors. That is, when we assume simple reproduction,

Intersectoral supply = demand of the means of production $v_1+m_1=c_2+c_c$

Intersectoral supply = demand of the means of consumption $c_2=v_1+m_1+v_c+m_c$

And substituting the second equation for the first equation leads $W_c=c_c+v_c+m_c=0$. It means that the commercial sector does not produce value at all.

This result can be taken in the case of extended reproduction where m_1 , m_2 and mc are divided into $m(c)+m(v)+m(k)$ respectively. In this case, this three sector reproduction scheme becomes

$$W_1=c_1+v_1+m_1(c)+m_1(v)+m_1(k)$$

$$W_2=c_2+v_2+m_2(c)+m_2(v)+m_2(k)$$

$$W_c=c_c+v_c+m_c(c)+m_c(v)+m_c(k)$$

And the intersectoral supply and demand of both goods become

Intersectoral supply = demand of the means of production

$$v_1+m_1(v)+m_1(k)=c_2+m_2(c)+c_c+m_c(c)$$

Intersectoral supply = demand of the means of consumption

$$c_2+m_2(c)=v_1+m_1(v)+m_1(k)+v_c+m_c(v)+m_c(k)$$

And substituting the second equation for the first equation leads

$W_c=c_c+v_c+m_c(c)+m_c(v)+m_c(k)=0$, that is $W_c=0$ again.

Of course, the commercial sector also actually spends the cost $c_c+v_c>0$, but this spending is not the 'productive' activity and therefore does not transfer and not formulate any value. Therefore, surplus value in this sector should be negative as $m_c=(c_c+v_c)<0$. It is because these costs are spent in the non-productive sector. This fact is now reconfirmed by this calculation result as $W_c=c_c+v_c+m_c=0$.

Role of the Commercial Sector and its Optimal Weight

However, the commercial sector can receive a part of surplus value from the productive sector by shortening the time of circulation, and this relation could be formulated uniquely by Onishi (2015) in its second section of chapter five.

Onishi (2015)'s first step is to identify the contribution of commercial capital to industrial capital by reducing the time of circulation. Let us suppose Δp the original length of time of production, Δc the original length of time of circulation, $\Delta c'$ the reduced length of time of circulation due to the activities by commercial capital, with surplus value m originally produced by industrial capital. In this case, the industrial capital can lengthen its time of production

$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p}$ times longer, and additionally produce $\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} m$ amount of surplus value³.

³ Strictly speaking, following three assumptions are required for the above equation. That is, ① single-line continuous and constant production system which Marx explained in chapter 15, volume 2 of *Capital*, ② same $\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} = z$ in all the industrial sectors, ③ occupancy rate of the fixed capital is sufficiently

In this case, it also needs a certain additional production cost for its additional production, but this additional cost can be covered by its shortened turn-over.

Onishi (2015)'s second step is to identify the condition that this additional new surplus value can cover all the cost of the commercial sector and its profit. Let us suppose c_c , v_c and m_c transaction cost, wage and profit of the commercial capital⁴. In this case, this condition should be shown as.

$$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} m > c_c + v_c + m_c^5$$

Because this left side shows the additional surplus value produced by the industrial sectors, it also shows that the total production is also increased by them. $c+v+m$ of the commercial sector is covered by this additional production of the surplus value. In this case, representing the constant capital and variable capital of the industrial capital after introducing the commercial capital as c_p and v_p respectively, and assuming the equalized annual rate of profit r between two capital, above inequality can be transformed into

$$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} (c_p + v_p) \times \text{annual rate of profit} > (c_c + v_c) \{1 + \text{annual rate of profit}\}.$$

In the calculation of the annual rate of profit, the turn-over period must be taken into consideration as long as the shorten-

ing of the circulation period is discussed, and hence the annual rate of profit is set as r below. Here, r is a profit rate not considering the turn-over period. In this case, above inequality becomes

$$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} (c_p + v_p) r \left(\frac{1}{\Delta p + \Delta c} \right) > (c_c + v_c) \left\{ 1 + r \left(\frac{1}{\Delta p + \Delta c} \right) \right\},$$

and also transformed into an inequality which shows the ratio of total cost between both sectors. That is,

$$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} \cdot \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} > \frac{c_c + v_c}{c_p + v_p}$$

Until now we've discussed an individual industrial capital and commercial capital. However, this inequality can be changed to an equal sign if the scope of consideration is not limited to individual commercial capital, but applied to commercial capital in general. This is because when such commercial technology becomes widespread enough, less productive commercial capital will enter the field. Therefore, replacing this inequality sign with an equal sign, we can take.

$$\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p} \cdot \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} = \frac{c_c + v_c}{c_p + v_p}$$

It is very important to understand that this left side tends to rise under a given profit rate and turn-over period. It is because $\Delta c - \Delta c'$, Δp and $\Delta p + \Delta c$ tend to decrease by the technological progress. In Marxian economics, r tends to fall and therefore we cannot perceive whether the right side rises or not, but it is true that the weight of the commercial sector rises as far as under a given rate. Honestly, this conclusion is opposite from Marx's opinion that weight of the commercial sector fall due to the technological progress of the commercial sector which is expressed as the rise of m in this paper. Although Marx's opinion looks right intuitively, technological progress of the commercial sector makes this sector much useful, and therefore industrial sectors tend to use the commercial sector actively.

elastic. Although this paper does not lose these assumptions here, the reader should know it.

⁴ Marx identified storage and transport costs as expenses that are related to the original production activity, even though they are part of the distribution process. Consequently, even if these are paid by commercial capital, in this context they need to be understood as capital investments in the productive sectors that produce value, not in the commercial sector.

⁵ Onishi (2018) put only the commercial profit in the right side of the above inequality, but it is a mistake. Right side should be $c_c + v_c + m_c$.

Therefore, based on this conclusion, and by simbolizing $\frac{\Delta c - \Delta c'}{\Delta p}$ part as z for the latter manipulation, we can express simply

$$c_c + v_c = z \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} (c_1 + c_2 + v_1 + v_2).$$

Of course, under the condition where profit rates are equalized, it becomes

$$m_c = z \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} (m_1 + m_2).$$

Therefore, commercial sector in the reproduction scheme can be transformed as

$$\begin{aligned} W_c &= z \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} (c_1 + c_2 + v_1 + v_2) + z \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} (m_1 + m_2) \\ &= z \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} (c_1 + c_2 + v_1 + v_2 + m_1 + m_2) \\ &= z \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} (W_1 + W_2). \end{aligned}$$

Recalculation of c and v under the Equalized Profit-rate; Shibata-Okishio's Method

Above mentioned method solved the question what weight should be taken by the commercial sector to the industrial sectors (productive sectors), but still that commercial sector is not incorporated satisfactorily in the reproduction scheme, because 'r' is not still equalized in this form. Therefore, in order to do so, we need to introduce the equalization process of the profit rates of the three sectors. In this paper, we use Shibata and Okishio's method⁶ to equalize profit rates by recalculating transformed c and v. Therefore, we first introduce their method briefly for the readers.

Their method starts from the below two equation systems, that is

$$W_1 = c_1 + v_1 + m_1$$

$$W_2 = c_2 + v_2 + m_2,$$

and its first step to equalize profit rates is to transform them into

$$W_1' = (c_1 + v_1)(1 + r^0)$$

$$W_2' = (c_2 + v_2)(1 + r^0)$$

where r^0 expresses the first round equatization of this transformation, and W_1' and W_2' express the first round value of both sectors of this transformation. However, take a note that the above formation does not consider the problem of turn-over. This shortcoming will be solved in the next section.

However, because price change to W_1' and W_2' from W_1 and W_2 also changes the prices of constant capital and variable capital, we need to calculate new prices of c_1 , c_2 , v_1 and v_2 by a recalculation. Therefore,

$$W_1'' = (c_1 \frac{W_1'}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2'}{W_2})(1 + r^1)$$

$$W_2'' = (c_2 \frac{W_1'}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2'}{W_2})(1 + r^1)$$

where r^1 is a new average rate of profit. This is the second round of transformation, but, since the "redistribution" is not completed yet, we still have to look for another average rate of profit, r^2 , as expressed as follows:

$$W_1''' = (c_1 \frac{W_1''}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2''}{W_2})(1 + r^2)$$

$$W_2''' = (c_2 \frac{W_1''}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2''}{W_2})(1 + r^2)$$

This is the step by step recalculation, and what is finally obtained are the equal rate of profit, r^* , and each sector's sales, W_1^* and W_2^* . That is,

$$W_1^* = (c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2})(1 + r^*)$$

$$W_2^* = (c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2})(1 + r^*)$$

Shibata (1935) shows that this iterative calculation will converge, but take a note that all these transformation are just the redistribution which does not add any new value. Therefore, $W_1 + W_2 = W_1' + W_2' = W_1'' + W_2'' = W_1^* + W_2^*$. This identification and the above two equations determines three variables: W_1, W_2 and r .

⁶ See Shibata (1935) and Okishio (1972, 1973). In the Western world, this iterative method is well-known by Shaikh (1977), but it was introduced by Shibata and developed by Okishio.

Reproduction Scheme with Commercial Sector

Based on the above results, this final section finalizes the transformation of the three sector reproduction scheme with the commercial sector. For this purpose, first, we must set the original three equation system of the reproduction before the transformation. That is,

$$W_1 = c_1 + v_1 + m_1$$

$$W_2 = c_2 + v_2 + m_2$$

$$W_c = z \frac{r}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r} (c_1 + c_2 + v_1 + v_2 + m_1 + m_2).$$

Here, as seen in the second section, W_c amount of value is additionally produced by the industrial sectors. The form of the W_c sector comes from the result of the weight of the commercial sector calculated at the same section, and sets the profit rate 'r' as the annual rate of profit considering the periods of turn-over which are assumed equal between two industrial sectors. Furthermore, take a note of a strangeness that only the last equation includes 'r' but 'r' does not appear in the first two equations. That's why we need a transformation of this three equation system including the commercial sector.

The first step of this transformation change the above three equations into

$$W_1' = (c_1 + v_1) \left(1 + \frac{r^0}{\Delta p + \Delta c}\right)$$

$$W_2' = (c_2 + v_2) \left(1 + \frac{r^0}{\Delta p + \Delta c}\right)$$

$$W_c' = z \frac{r^0}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^0} (c_1 + c_2 + v_1 + v_2) \left(1 + \frac{r^0}{\Delta p + \Delta c}\right) = z (c_1 + c_2 + v_1 + v_2) \frac{r^0}{\Delta p + \Delta c}.$$

As mentioned above, because W_c' is the value produced by the industrial sector additionally after the introduction of the commercial sector, still $W_1' + W_2'$ is same with $W_1 + W_2$. Therefore, $W_1' + W_2' = W_1 + W_2$ and the first two equations can solve three variables: W_1', W_2' and r^0 , and later this r^0 determines W_c' . In other words, the first two equations are independent from the last equation.

However, as we see, this transformation is not enough, and then go to the next three equations as

$$W_1'' = \left(c_1 \frac{W_1''}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2''}{W_2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{r^1}{\Delta p + \Delta c}\right)$$

$$W_2'' = \left(c_2 \frac{W_1''}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2''}{W_2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{r^1}{\Delta p + \Delta c}\right)$$

$$W_c'' = z \left(c_1 \frac{W_1''}{W_1} + c_2 \frac{W_1''}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2''}{W_2} + v_2 \frac{W_2''}{W_2}\right) \frac{r^1}{\Delta p + \Delta c}$$

And then, after some steps, we can finalized this transformation process as the result of

$$W_1^* = \left(c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c}\right)$$

$$W_2^* = \left(c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2}\right) \left(1 + \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c}\right)$$

$$W_c^* = z \left(c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2}\right) \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c}$$

This result shows several important points. These are,

1. As seen in the first step of this transformation, the first two equations and supposed $W_1^* + W_2^* = W_1 + W_2$ can determine three variables: W_1^* , W_2^* and r^* independent from the commercial sector. In other words, the commercial sector does not commit to the determination of the equal profit rate at all but just accepts.

2. Total sale of the commercial sector W_c^* can be rewritten as $z \frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*} (W_1^* + W_2^*)$ which shows that $\frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*}$ times larger than the total production of the industrial sectors.

3. Of course, profit of the commercial sector also should be $\frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*}$ times larger than the total profit of the industrial sectors, and $\frac{r^*}{(\Delta p + \Delta c) + r^*}$ is determined partly by the existing technologies Δp , Δc and $\Delta c'$ and partly by r^* which is determined by the industrial sectors.

We can translate the above three equations into $c+v+m$ type of formation as

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_1^* &= c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} + \left(c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \right) \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c} \\
 W_2^* &= c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} + \left(c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \right) \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c} \\
 W_c^* &= c_c \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_c \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \\
 &\quad + \left\{ z \left(c_1 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + c_2 \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_1 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} + v_2 \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \right) \frac{r^*}{\Delta p + \Delta c} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \left(c_c \frac{W_1^*}{W_1} + v_c \frac{W_2^*}{W_2} \right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

The last equation of this system can show the complexity to determine the profit rate in the commercial sector.

In conclusion, we could show that 1) surplus value in the commercial sector is not produced in this sector but just redis-

tributed from the industrial sector, but 2) the commercial sector can improve the production of the surplus value by shortening the circulation period for the industrial sector, and 3) the commercial sector can take a certain weight in the whole economy based on some conditions such as period of production (Δp), period of circulation (Δc) and shortening ratio of period of circulation ($\Delta c - \Delta c'$), and finally 4) average profit rate is determined only by the industrial sectors independent of the commercial sectors.

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